

THE ROLE OF COACHING TECHNOLOGY IN THE DEVELOPMENT
OF CREATIVE THINKING AND ABILITIES OF ADULTS IN
LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10279082>

Annotation: this article deals with demonstrating the importance of thinking abilities, as well as, implementing them into practice in language learning process. On the top of that it can give basic data about the role of coaching technology in learning process and developing ways in this field.

Key words: foreign language, playing, English, creative thinking, development, ability, student, critical thinking, project technology, creative ability of students.

Foreign language plays a huge role in the formation of the personality, its development, because with the help of it is possible to gain direct access to the spiritual wealth of another country. The way and scope of information perception has changed, so it is necessary to change approaches to training [1, p. 11]. Foreign language is one of the subjects that helps the deep development of the student 's personality. Teaching at the modern stage is a process of development of students, development of creative thinking, his creative abilities. And the main task of the school is to develop and form the personality of schoolchildren. We face one of the most difficult challenges - creating an environment conducive to the formation of the personality of each child. We want to show the means that help us solve one of the main tasks of education - to teach students to work in and out of the lesson, to awaken interest in his soul, to make teaching strong and joyful, to educate the person with developed creative thinking. The question "How to achieve maximum creative and intellectual development of the person?" should become the leading teacher in the work. The availability of professional knowledge on the use of modern pedagogical technologies, techniques and methods of working with them helps the teacher to successfully solve this task. Pedagogical technologies, with the help of which it is possible to realize new requirements, are well-known technologies: problem training, project training, information and communication technologies, game technologies, communicative technologies, technology of development of critical thinking through reading and writing. Intellectual development of the pupil, development of his emotional sphere takes place by learning English from the first steps of learning. English

instruction is initially based on gaming technology.

In our lessons we apply a variety of games, developing intelligence, memory and creativity of the child: grammar games, lexical games, phonetic games, role- playing games (creative games), spelling games. Among them are games such as "Magic Box," Blind Owl, "Most Aggressive," Crosses-Noliki, "Overtake Me," game-project, etc. And, for example, when studying the topic "Professions and necessary qualities for its mastery" better reception than business game is not found. The teacher can hand out the roles of interviewer and interviewee, teach to write resumes and job announcements. Interactive teaching methods are based on the encouragement of practical and thought activities, without which there is no movement forward in the knowledge and development of the pupil as a whole. The child's abilities develop in the game. The game requires a strain of mental strength. The fact that the pupil also speaks a foreign language is positive. Emotional is easily connected to artistic. The theatrical, musical, literary or other activities of children when teaching a foreign language not only develop their genuine interest and desire to learn, but also have a positive impact on the development of attention, memory, thinking, imagination [2, c.12]. In the game, a child under the pressure of argument and objection begins to try to justify his thought in the eyes of others and begins to observe his own thinking. Educational and developing reserves of foreign language as a subject of school curriculum are most fully revealed in conditions of activity approach, which is the basis of project technology.

Purpose of project technology introduction: creation of conditions for formation of research skills of students, contributing to development of creative abilities and logical thinking; Contribute to improving the quality of education and education. The organization of any educational project involves the organization of creative activities of students, which is the main condition for the formation of the individual. Our students are interested in creating cool projects on UMK "New Matrix," Starlight, "Forward." The project training technology actively affects the development of the motivational sphere of the trainee. In the work on the project children learn to cooperate, and this brings up in them such moral values as mutual assistance, desire and ability to empathize, creative abilities and activity of students are formed, that is, there is an inextricable process of education and education. Projects are one of the most successful forms of development of the subject, developing reclusive activity of pupils of keen interest and healthy excitement. Involving students in project activities, we wanted each of them to develop and use their deposits as much as

possible already in school. Interesting works on projects were: "London-city of my dreams," Traditions of claiming names in England and Russia, "Holidays of Russia." Children prepared interesting posters, booklets, slide presentations, created a directory of history of names of the family. Working on projects "Great Britain," American holidays, "English cuisine," Travel in America, "children produced very interesting advertising prospectus, photo reports. The active incentive to learn can be the inclusion of students in collective activities, through the acceptance of "trial and error method."

For example, when studying word-exceptions in the subject "Plural nouns," we ask if a student knows how to form plural nouns, the Answer is certainly affirmative. Then we propose to form a plural of nouns such as child, tool, family, etc. Pupils make mistakes. The teacher demonstrates the correct education, the students express surprise, a problematic situation arises, thus the students themselves define a new topic of the lesson. These classes help students to take initiative, take risks, carry out creative activities. We often work with our students using information and communication technologies (ICT). The use of ICT in English lessons allows you to train different types of speech activities and combine them in different combinations. The variety of topics and activities, colorful, fascinating and accessible computer tasks help to effectively develop the different communicative skills of students. All our students willingly work with the computer, with a desire to participate in the creation of slide presentations, projects, with pleasure to perform computer tests, use electronic directories and dictionaries. Internet educational resources are also used to prepare the project. The use of ICT contributes to the development of creativity, autonomy and helps to demonstrate their research abilities. The use of critical thinking technology through reading and writing provides significant assistance in developing the personality of students, as such lessons develop the creative abilities of students.

The techniques of interest to our learners are: Sinquein, Fishbone, Raft, Insert, Six Hats, Cluster. It has been proven that the process of learning a foreign language contributes to the development of mental abilities. We convince children that it is possible to study and understand other subjects and even exact disciplines, such as mathematics, physics, chemistry, etc., as learning a foreign language requires remembering and understanding several thousand new words and concepts, as a result of which the brain gets good training. And this will help to preserve a good memory until deep old age. Our students often get creative tasks, for example: name a plant that is part of all subsequent words

that denote a sack for keeping hop, a game for children, an event in sport, the name of an animal, the place where this plant grows, a person of a very small height. In order to complete such tasks, students must work with the dictionary. This exercise can be served as a crossword, as a mystery. All you have to do is turn on the imagination. Working with the dictionary is an inexhaustible source for creating a type of creative assignment such as finding English polyndromes. And students have to come up with a clue to the found polyndromes: a heroic action - deed a lady - madam a signal for help - SOS a boy 's name - Bob a strong stroke - pop One of the favorite activities of our children is to invent riddles in verses in English. First we choose the object of the conversation and a pair of rhymes, then a creative process follows.

FROG SPIDER I am slippy, green and fat. I can frighten everybody. I am ugly like a rat. I can bite your trembling body. I can croak from the log. I can move with all my legs. I am a poor little... (frog) I can weave a lot of webs. We consider the exercises on finding "false twins" to be an interesting and useful work in this direction. Students make a "false twins" file and then make sentences with the found couple. FOUR — FOR EAT — IT Four of us worked for pleasure. It usually likes to eat it. Some difficulty in the creative work of students is caused by exercises such as "Catch the word." They require complex mental labor, the presence of lexical-grammatical skills. However, with a variety of topics, many different job variants can be created. Subject: "Fauna". Make a task: find the names of animals and insects in the proposals you propose. I want to do good exercises. (dog) This man tried to help me. (A nt) Another effective means of developing students 'creative thinking and creativity is through their work in research societies. Our students choose the topic of research, collect and analyze the obtained material, search using modern methods and techniques, make presentations. This type of work of students is based on fruitful active activity, developing not only the emotional sphere of the child, but also his creative abilities, thinking. In the process of work they synthesize, classify, analyze the received information, learn to prove the set hypothesis, achieve the goal and solve multiple problems.

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